

Spectroscopic Studies on some Hydroxy-nitrosocoumarins

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Some coumarin derivatives exhibit distinct physiological photodynamic and bacteriostatic activities¹. Besides, they have a number of uses². Introduction of nitroso group to monohydroxycoumarins increases their chelating tendency. 3-Nitroso-4-hydroxycoumarin is closely related analytical reagent containing the chelating group HO-C=C-NO³.

In the present study, nitroso group was introduced in the phenyl moiety of some coumarin derivatives. Ir, ¹H, ¹³C nmr and mass spectral studies were performed to throw some light on their structures 1-5.

- 1, 5-CH₃, 7-OH, 8-NO (7-hydroxy-4,5-dimethyl-8-nitrosocoumarin)
 2, 5-NO, 6-OH, 7-CH₃ (6-hydroxy-4,7-dimethyl-5-nitrosocoumarin)
 3, 5-OH, 6-NO, 7-CH₃ (5-hydroxy-4,7-dimethyl-6-nitrosocoumarin)
 4, 7-OH, 8-NO (7-hydroxy-4-methyl-8-nitrosocoumarin)
 5, 5,7-di-NO, 6-OH (6-hydroxy-4-methyl-5,7-dinitrosocoumarin)

Results and Discussion

Mass spectra : The parent coumarin compound exhibits an abundant molecular ion (*m/z* 146), and there is no other very facile bond cleavage available. The loss of a stable neutral molecule of carbon monoxide is a very important fragmentation process, resulting in the base peak (*m/z* 118)⁴. The subsequent fragmentation of the M-CO ion by a loss of a second molecule of carbon monoxide followed by a hydrogen atom gives *m/z* 89. The fragmentation pattern of 7-hydroxycoumarin resembles that of coumarin itself⁵. The oxygen atom of the hydroxyl group is lost as CO. It was reported also that 7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin losses CO and H⁺ from the methyl group⁵.

The molar ion M⁺ indicates the existence of combined water molecules. The elemental analyses of compounds 1-4 show the existence of half water molecule in each compound. The calculated molecular weights for 1-4 are 228, 228, 228 and 214 respectively. Their base peaks at 228, 228, 228 and 214 are close to the calculated values. For compound 5 the calculated value of 260 by elemental analysis, indicates the existence of one-and-half water molecules.

Ir spectra : The ir spectra of the hydroxynitrosocoumarins (1-5)⁶⁻⁹ are recorded in Table 1. It can be concluded from the data that the two oxygens will be *cis* in dimerisation of the compounds under investigation¹⁰.

Nmr spectra : A further support for the results is gained by considering the nmr spectral data of 1-5 (Table 2). The signals observed at 9.7-11.2 are assigned to the proton of the hydroxyl group in the aromatic ring in all the investigated compounds. This proton is ionisable proton, thus upon addition of deuterium oxide (D₂O) to the above ligands, the signal corresponding to the OH group disappeared with the appearance of another signal at δ 3.6-4.2 due to HOD. The water of crystallisation appeared at δ 3.2-3.4. The integration curves show one proton in each case except compound 5 which showed three protons. Accordingly, the existence of such water molecules was confirmed by elemental analysis, mass and nmr spectra.

TABLE 1-Ir SPECTRAL DATA (cm⁻¹) OF COMPOUNDS 1-5

1	2	3	4	5	Assignment
3 211	3 171	3 420	3 498	3 331	νOH
3 090	3 060	3 070	3 079	3 079	Aromatic C-H str.
2 920	2 920	2 925	2 950	2 920	Aliphatic C-H str ^a
1 740	1 697	1 745	1 710	1 730	C=O
1 612	1 627	1 610	1 617	1 631	C=C ^b
1 527	1 540	1 560	1 530	1 571	C=C ^b
1 467	1 490	1 449	1 487	1 466	C=C ^b
1 442	1 434	1 406	1 452	1 439	Assym. CH ₃ def.
1 383	1 358	1 355	1 365	1 355	Sym. CH ₃ def.
1 358	1 378	1 377	1 391	1 379	N=O (dimmer <i>cis</i>) ^c
1 311	1 343	1 331	1 331	1 312	N=O (dimmer <i>trans</i>) ^c
1 291	1 270	1 277	1 277	1 253	C-N asym ^d .
1 245	1 208	1 212	1 224	1 200	C-O asym.
1 180	1 173	1 173	1 159	1 163	C-N sym ^d
1 100	1 067	1 082	1 096	1 117	δOH
1 030	1 028	1 055	1 054	1 054	C-O sym.
899	896	871	867	888	γCH ^e
800	787	785	810	821	γOH

^aRef. 9. ^bRef. 7. ^cRef. 11. ^dRef. 8. ^eRef. 10

¹³C nmr spectra : The screening of ¹³C nuclei has a linear relation to the π-electron density and a change in the charge by one electron produces a resonance shift of 160 ppm¹¹. As in proton resonance, additivity of the chemical shift of ¹³C is observed in benzene derivatives¹² and in the

case of these nuclei the range of investigations is extended due to the possibility of studying the effect of a substituent which is attached directly to the given carbon atom. The additivity of the chemical shifts and their relation to the electronegativity of substituents in the aliphatic series is much more approximate in character. But this may be related to the difficulties of taking account of other factors.

In contrast to acetylene, the carbon atoms of aromatic rings give a signal in the same region as alkene carbons. The absence of an anisotropy in this case is undoubtedly due to the fact that the carbon atoms of the ring lie at the boundary of the region of screening produced by ring currents. The low field position of the region of chemical shifts of a carbonyl carbon is evidently due primarily to the descreening effect of the electronegative oxygen and not to the anisotropy of the C=O band

TABLE 2—¹H NMR SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 1-5

Comp. no.	δ	Assignment
1	11.1	OH
	8.2	Aromatic C-H ^a
	6.4	Pyrone ring C-H ^b
	3.4	H ₂ O of crystallisation
	2.4	CH ₃ of aromatic ring
	2.2	CH ₃ of pyrone ring
2	9.7	OH
	7.4	Aromatic C-H ^a
	6.5	Pyrone ring C-H ^b
	3.2	H ₂ O of crystallisation
	2.3	CH ₃ of aromatic ring
	2.2	CH ₃ of pyrone ring
3	11.2	OH
	7.0	Aromatic C-H ^a
	6.3	Pyrone ring C-H ^b
	3.2	H ₂ O of crystallisation
	2.6	CH ₃ of aromatic ring
	2.3	CH ₃ of pyrone ring
4	10.5	OH
	7.5	Aromatic C-H ^a
	6.7	Aromatic C-H ^a
	6.1	Pyrone ring C-H ^b
	3.2	H ₂ O of crystallisation
	2.3	CH ₃ of pyrone ring
5	11.1	OH
	8.2	Aromatic C-H ^a
	6.7	Pyrone ring C-H ^b
	2.3	CH ₃ of pyrone ring

^aRef. 14. ^bRef. 13.

The ¹³C nmr spectra of 1 is characterised by the presence of two signals at 17.8 and 8.4 ppm, the first corresponding to the CH₃ of the pyrone ring¹³ and the latter to the CH₃ of the aromatic ring. The other signals observed are in good agreement with those obtained previously on dimethylcoumarin¹⁴. The low-field position of the region of the carbon attached to OH or NO is due to the effect of

the electronegative oxygen or nitrogen atoms like the case of C=O group. C-9 and C-10 could be easily differentiated by the downfield shift of C-9 arising from the attached oxygen¹⁵. The chemical shift value of C-3 was found to be smaller than that C-4 because C-3 is not in conjugation with the C-2 carbonyl function¹⁶. Also the same results were obtained with ligand 3, the signals observed at 23.3 and 17.2 ppm corresponding to the CH₃ of the aromatic ring and CH₃ of the pyrone ring respectively, the downfield shift of the CH₃ of the aromatic ring may be due to the presence of a nitroso group at C-6¹³. The other signals observed are in the same order like those obtained earlier¹⁴. In compound 5 only one signal was observed at 17.1 ppm corresponding to the CH₃ of the pyrone ring. The spectra are characterised by the presence of the signals like those obtained earlier¹⁴. The deviation from the results found in literature¹⁷ for 4-methylcoumarin with respect to the investigated ligands is due to the substitution of OH and NO groups in the aromatic ring which lead to downfield shift.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of C.P. grade. 7-Hydroxy-4,5-dimethylcoumarin, 5-hydroxy-4,7-dimethylcoumarin and 7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin¹⁶, 6-hydroxy-4,7-dimethylcoumarin and 6-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin¹⁸ were prepared according to the reported methods. Nitrosation of the above five compounds were carried out by passing NO gas liberated from the addition of concentrated HCl to NaNO₂ to the cooled suspension of the coumarin derivatives in acetic acid and acetic anhydride till the solution became clear; the reaction mixture was kept at 0° during nitrosation. The mixture was then poured with vigorous stirring into a mixture of crushed ice and water. The resulting yellow solids were washed with water, dried and crystallised from 75% ethanol : 1, m.p. 230°; 2, 180°; 3, 230°; 4, 170°; 5, 210°.

Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 1430 spectrophotometer. ¹H nmr spectra (DMSO-d₆) on a Varian Gemini spectrometer (200-200 MHz) using TMS as internal standard, ¹³C nmr spectra on a Bruker WM-250 MHz spectrometer and mass spectra on a Joel-JMS-BS-300 spectrometer at 70 eV and 100 MA energy using a direct insertion probe at 90–110°.

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